

Scrub Typhus Public Engagement - Translation of the Thai flipchart text into English language

Description:

These flipcharts were designed to be used by community health volunteers in Northern Thailand to explain community members under their responsibility about scrub typhus transmission, risk factors, prevention and management. They were part of a scrub typhus public engagement project.

The flipcharts are so printed that when a particular picture is shown to an audience, a corresponding picture with a text description is visible to the person who is teaching. The two are described as “front” and “back” in the translations. below.

<p><i>Flipchart title page:</i> Scrub Typhus disease</p> <p>By:</p> <p>The Mahidol - Oxford Tropical Research Unit, the Primary Care Department of Chiang Rai Prachanukroh Hospital together with the Chiang Rai Provincial Public Health office</p>
<p>Scrub Typhus disease</p> <p><i>1st picture, front</i> [Depiction of woman in traditional Akha headdress showing eschar wound to fellow farmer]</p> <p><i>1st picture, back</i> [microscopic pictures of <i>Orientia tsutsugamushi</i> infecting cells]:</p> <p>Kai Rak Sat Yai [<i>Thai name for Scrub Typhus</i>], known in the medical field as Scrub Typhus, is a disease caused by an infection with a type of bacteria called <i>Orientia tsutsugamushi</i> (also known as <i>O. tsutsugamushi</i>)</p>
<p>Disease vector</p> <p><i>2nd picture, front</i> [Depiction of rat with a mite attached to its inner ear]</p> <p><i>2nd picture, back</i> [Photos of rat with chigger clusters attached to its inner ear]: These are chigger mites, they act as carriers to bring the afore mentioned pathogen to humans by burrowing into the skin</p>
<p>The pathogen is carried by rodents</p> <p><i>3rd picture, front</i> [Depiction of several rodents in a forest]:</p> <p><i>3rd picture, back</i> [Photos of several rodents]: Chigger mites often bite and feed on lymph fluid and reside in rodent hosts, such as mice and rats</p>
<p>Risk environments for the disease</p> <p><i>4th picture, front</i> [Depiction of waterfall and several risk environments]</p> <p><i>4th picture, back</i> [Photos of waterfall and other risk environments]: Areas prone to infection People can become infected when they enter a place where the mite larvae live. It can be a forest area, areas adjacent to agricultural land, farmland or places near waterfalls and rivers.</p>
<p>Risk factors for the disease</p>

5th picture, front [Depiction of coffee and tea picking and other risk activities]

5th picture, back [Photos of coffee picking and some risk environments]:

If we enter the area where these animals live, it may cause us to get infected as well if we are bitten by larvae.

Symptoms of infection

6th picture, front [Depiction of scrub typhus symptoms]

6th picture, back [Pictures of fever, vomiting and headache]:

Symptoms of infection

Approximately 6-21 days after being bitten by an infected larva, the symptoms will be fever, headache, nausea, vomiting, cough, rash, tinnitus, fatigue, muscle weakness, red eyes, enlarged lymph nodes and enlarged spleen. If treated late, complications affecting the liver, lungs, blood system, central nervous system, kidneys, heart, and death may follow.

Symptoms of infection

7th picture, front [Depiction of several children with eschars]

7th picture, back [Photos of eschars]

In addition to the symptoms mentioned above, signs from patients can also be found. The patient will have a black burn-like scab wound, similar to a cigarette burn, which begins as a blister at the bite site, develops into a wound and progresses to necrosis, often without pain.

Lesions appear on the body in warm, humid areas or under underwear: groin, armpits, ears external genitalia, waist, thighs, neck, abdomen and breasts [are common areas]. They are found in only 30% of patients. Some of them [the patients] may not have cigarette-burn marks [eschars].

Treatment

8th picture, front [Depiction of mother and child going to a primary care unit]

8th picture, back [Photos of primary care units]

Treatment

If you suspect that you are sick with this disease, hurry to see the medical service staff.

Patients with mild to moderate symptoms can also be treated [as outpatients] with specific antibiotics without needing to be hospitalized.

Symptoms we should worry about

9th picture, front [Depiction of hospitalised patient]

9th picture, back [photos of a hospital]

Patients with rapid breathing Abnormal vital signs, bleeding, shock, confusion or loss of consciousness, stiff-neck, yellow skin or little urination need to see a doctor as soon as possible and may need to be hospitalized.

Don't go buy treatment by yourself

10th picture, front [Depiction of mother buying medicine at a pharmacy, with a cross superimposed]

10th picture, back [Photos of a pharmacy, with a cross superimposed]

Scrub typhus disease

Specific antibiotics must be used for treatment. Conventional antibiotics cannot cure it. Therefore, do not go and buy your own medicine.

Disease prevention

11th picture, front: [Depiction of father and child in a field wearing protective clothing and taking a shower]

11th picture, back [Photo of a man wearing protective clothing while spraying insecticide in a field and a photo of rubber boots]

Prevention

Due to the absence of a preventive vaccine and the short duration of immunity, infections can spread continuously. Therefore, for individuals residing in areas where the disease has been detected, preventive measures should be taken as follows:

- 1-Wear tight-fitting protective clothing while going to work, such as long-sleeved shirts, long pants, socks, boots, scarves, hats, and gloves.
- 2- Immediately take a shower after finishing agricultural work, using soap to thoroughly clean your body.

Disease prevention

12th picture, front: [Depiction of a woman cleaning the work clothes of her husband]

12th picture, back [Photo of a person removing a jumper and of clothes being washed]

3-After returning from work in areas at risk of disease transmission, change your clothes immediately and separate the worn clothes to be laundered. Do not mix them with the clothes you wear inside the house.

Disease prevention

13th picture, front: [Depiction of people kneeling to the ground while working the land, with a red cross superimposed]

13th picture, back [Photos of people in a crouched position]

4-When working, avoid bending down and kneeling onto the ground

Disease prevention

14th picture, front: [Depiction of people lying on the ground and on haystacks, with a red cross superimposed]

14th picture, back [Photos of people lying on haystacks or on the ground in a crouched position]

During breaks, avoid sitting or lying on the ground. Do not sit or lie on grass or haystacks.

If possible, avoid places with high numbers of mites and rodents such as haystacks, forest edges, areas where new weeds grow next to forests or waterways.